

CORPORATE REAL ESTATE MANAGEMENT: A KEY DRIVER OF ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN BAUCHI'S BANKING SECTOR

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Abstract: Corporate real estate management (CREM) plays a vital role in enhancing organizational competitiveness and productivity. A research gap exists in understanding the specific CREM strategies adopted by banks in Bauchi Metropolis, Nigeria, and their direct impact on organizational performance. This study aims to address this gap by investigating CREM practices in the banking sector, focusing on its influence on performance. The study utilized a quantitative approach, collecting data from 78 staff across various banks in Bauchi Metropolis. It employed a stratified random sampling technique and a structured questionnaire with 5-point Likert-scale questions to measure respondents' perceptions on the impact of CREM practices on organizational productivity and performance; the key CREM variables affecting productivity and performance and understanding stakeholders' perceptions of CREM's added value. The study revealed that banks in Bauchi Metropolis recognized the significance of several CREM strategies. Moreover, tailoring CREM strategies to the local context was seen as vital for success. In terms of organizational performance, respondents agreed that effective CREM positively influenced financial performance, cost reduction, operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, and the bank's reputation. The study concludes that CREM significantly benefits the banking sector in Bauchi Metropolis, positively affecting performance across various aspects. To maximize these benefits, banks should adapt CREM strategies, foster innovation in workplaces, and implement evidence-based practices.

Keywords: Corporate Real Estate, Banking Organization, Performance, Productivity.

Introduction

The concept of Corporate Real Estate Management (CREM) has a historical background dating back to ancient civilizations, but it began to take its modern form during the 19th century with the rise of large-scale enterprises and urbanization (Glatte, 2021).

In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, companies in Nigeria, expanded their operations, leading to increased property acquisitions, although CREM was managed informally within individual departments at that time (Oyedokun, 2017). It was not until the early 20th century that companies recognized the need for specialized expertise in managing real estate assets (Sanderson & Read, 2020).

Corporate Real Estate (CRE) encompasses physical properties and assets such as office buildings, industrial facilities, and land holdings that corporations and large organizations use for their core activities (Saiz, 2020). CRE is considered a critical component of a company's asset portfolio, playing a pivotal role in supporting its business strategies (Echeverri *et al.*, 2021; Pfnuer & Seger, 2021). While, Corporate Real Estate Management (CREM) is defined as the strategic planning, acquisition, development, utilization, and optimization of real estate assets within organizations to support business objectives, enhance operational efficiency, and maximize financial performance (BoakyeAgyeman *et al.*, 2022). It operates at the intersection of corporate strategy, finance, and real estate, aiming to align the use of physical assets with the overall organizational goals (Nanda, 2021).

The theoretical bases for this study include the Resource-Based View (RBV), which suggests that real estate assets, like other resources, contribute to a firm's competitive advantage (Cuthbertson & Furseth, 2022) and Transaction Cost Economics (TCE) emphasizes the role of CREM in reducing transaction costs associated with property transactions (Syed *et al.*, 2023).

Additionally, Institutional Theory explores how external institutions and regulations influence CREM strategies and decisionmaking within organizations (Gupta *et al.*, 2020).

Corporate Real Estate Management (CREM) significantly contributes to creating conducive work environments, fostering innovation, ensuring employee well-being, promoting flexibility, optimizing costs, and encouraging sustainable business practices (Barakat, 2021). Efficient space utilization strategies improve employee productivity by facilitating collaboration, minimizing distractions, and enhancing workflows

(Tanpipat *et al.*, 2021). Factors like lighting, ventilation, and ergonomic design in CREM practices contribute to healthier and more comfortable workspaces, resulting in higher job satisfaction, reduced stress, and increased employee engagement (Jensen & van der Voordt, 2020).

Flexibility in physical spaces, such as remote work and collaborative zones, aligns resources with market demands, leading to improved employee satisfaction and productivity (Roth & Mirchandani, 2016). Additionally, strategic CREM initiatives help organizations optimize costs, thereby enhancing financial stability (Kämpf-Dern & Pfnür, 2014).

Despite the significant influence of CREM on organizational performance, it still encounters several challenges including regulatory compliance, cost optimization, technological integration, adaptability, and sustainability (Voordt & Jensen, 2018). According to Sulaiman *et al.* (2021), one challenge involves the necessity for strategic corporate real estate risk management to enhance performance.

Another hurdle is the incomplete adoption of strategic CRE management practices in certain organizations, suggesting that CRE is not managed strategically like other corporate resources (Pfnuer *et al.*, 2021).

Furthermore, the real estate industry encounters capital restraints, which could potentially impede enterprise survival and competitiveness (Alfaraj, 2019). Studies by Kaluthanthri, (2009); Tudzi *et al.*, (2015);

Mthabela and Ndlovu (2018); BoakyeAgyeman and Bugri (2019) and Vande Putte and Jylhä (2023) highlight that CREM in the banking sector is presently under-managed and lacks prominence in most companies. Notably, nearly one-third of Nigerian Banks lack a defined CREM strategy, as revealed by Oladokun and Aluko (2015).

Additionally, Oladokun and Aluko (2012) found that real estate employees in Nigerian Banks spend more time on core business activities than on real estate tasks.

Navigating these challenges is vital for operational efficiency and the long-term success of financial institutions, as emphasized by various authors. According to Pfnür *et al.*, (2019), adopting secure technology, optimizing costs, promoting adaptability, and investing in sustainability initiatives enable banks to establish a resilient foundation for success in the competitive financial landscape. To enhance CREM in the banking sector, a proactive approach to corporate real estate management is recommended. This proactive stance should be complemented by a

thorough exploration of the relationship between space-use efficiency and the implementation of technological innovations, as highlighted by Amos and Boakye-Agyeman (2023).

Therefore, this study addresses a significant research gap by conducting an empirical investigation into the banking sector in Bauchi Metropolis. The focus is on CREM strategies and practices within this context. The primary objective is to assess the impact of CREM practices on organizational productivity and performance; to identify key CREM variables affecting productivity and performance and to understand stakeholder perceptions of CREM's added value in the Banking Sector of Bauchi Metropolis respectively, specifically concerning cost optimization, efficient space utilization, and employee satisfaction.

Furthermore, the study endeavours to contribute valuable insights to the existing literature by exploring the relationship between corporate real estate management and its overall contribution to the competitiveness and performance of banks in Bauchi Metropolis, Nigeria. Through this extensive analysis, the study seeks to advance the understanding of the pivotal role played by CREM in shaping the success and competitive advantage of banks operating within the region.

Related Literature

The literature reviewed essential studies and research findings investigating the impact of CREM on organizational efficiency, employee productivity, and overall business success. It focuses on essential areas such as the strategies utilized in CREM, aligning CREM with organizational objectives for enduring success, and examining the intricate relationship between CREM and bank profitability.

Extensive exploration in the literature highlights that aligning real estate strategies with organizational objectives empowers businesses to attain financial efficiency, enhance employee and customer satisfaction, elevate their global reputation, and contribute to a sustainable future. CREM strategies and practices have become increasingly important in today's competitive business environment, as they affect the financial, operational, and competitive performance of organizations. However, CREM also faces various challenges and complexities in different contexts and markets. Therefore, it is important to examine the existing literature on CREM strategies and practices in different regions and sectors.

Recent studies in CREM shed light on various strategic approaches and challenges faced by organizations worldwide. The research conducted by Ali and Anwar (2021) aimed to investigate strategic management methods in Erbil's real estate industry. Employing a quantitative methodology, the study gathered crucial information about strategic management in real estate organizations in Erbil, capital of Iraqi, Kurdistan. Their findings highlighted cost leadership as the most effective strategy for real estate businesses in Erbil. They recommended further exploration of a combination of cost leadership and differentiation strategy due to Erbil's severe economic and financial crisis.

The study emphasized the implementation of acquisition strategies to prevent bank bankruptcy and liquidation. Similarly, Boakye-Agyeman *et al.* (2022) focused on the challenges faced in managing corporate real estate in Ghana, emphasizing strategic aspects. The study underscored the significance of effective corporate real estate management, providing recommendations to overcome identified challenges. They stressed that effective corporate real estate management is crucial for organizations in Ghana, directly impacting their overall performance and competitiveness.

The authors identified several challenges in strategic corporate real estate management in Ghana, including inadequate data, lack of awareness about the strategic role of real estate, and limited financial resources. They emphasized the need for organizations to develop a strategic approach to real estate management, aligning it with their overall business objectives.

In the banking sector, Do and Lee (2020) asserted that corporate real estate management strategies and practices adopted by banks vary based on specific needs and objectives. Their empirical analysis, using data from Vietnamese-listed banks between 2007 and 2017, revealed a positive relationship between corporate governance and bank performance in Vietnamese-listed banks. The study highlighted the importance of board size, indicating that smaller boards were more effective in improving bank performance. Additionally, the research found that ownership concentration and foreign ownership had mixed effects on bank performance, suggesting the need for further investigation.

In the same vein, Osmadi and Kaluthanthri (2019) conducted a literature review to identify common forms of corporate real estate strategies for different business sectors. The study identified seven mostly cited corporate real estate strategies applicable to business organizations. The authors presented sustainable CREM practices and components related to sustainable performance measurement. They integrated a sustainable theory balancing environmental, economic, and social impacts, forming a preliminary framework for Corporate Real Estate Sustainable Management.

Additionally, Fauzi *et al.* (2017) aimed to explore and summarize sustainable corporate real estate management practices and components of sustainable performance measurement. They identified 14 key strategies in Corporate Real Estate Sustainable Management (CREM), ranging from cost minimization and flexibility to promoting marketing messages, supporting environmental sustainability, and ensuring employee satisfaction. The research established 15 indicators to measure sustainable performance, covering economic, ecological, and social aspects. These findings were organized into a comprehensive framework model for CREM. The study employed content analysis, examining the literature and previous studies to formulate these insights.

While the framework provided a preliminary guide for sustainable corporate real estate management, further research was

encouraged to uncover context-specific best practices. Furthermore, Haynes *et al.* (2017) focused on the successful and efficient use of corporate office space, presenting a tenpoint CREM model covering various aspects such as sustainability, workplace productivity, real estate performance measurement, change management, and customer focus.

The study included new case studies illustrating how corporations actively manage their corporate real estate in the UK, USA, Hong Kong, and Abu Dhabi. The authors concentrated on the occupier's perspective, emphasizing the importance of implementing effective strategies in corporate real estate asset management.

They provided practical insights and case studies to support these strategies. These studies collectively contribute to the evolving landscape of CREM, offering valuable perspectives on tailored strategies, challenges, and innovative solutions. However, future research should prioritize larger sample sizes, diverse methodologies, and comparative analyses across regions and sectors to enrich the field further.

Having a defined CREM strategy in organizations can provide several benefits. According to Khan *et al.* (2022), it helps improve customer services and

responsiveness to customer needs, leading to increased customer satisfaction and loyalty. It also enables personalized service and customer segmentation, allowing organizations to tailor their marketing efforts and offerings to individual customers (Lokuge *et al.*, 2020). It facilitates multichannel integration, which enhances the customer experience by providing seamless interactions across different channels (Alnofeli *et al.*, 2023).

Additionally, a defined CREM strategy according to Munawar *et al.* (2020), saves time by streamlining processes and improving efficiency. It also enhances customer knowledge, enabling organizations to better understand their customers' needs and preferences (Low *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, a well-implemented CREM strategy can lead

to improved organizational performance by leveraging knowledge management and customer relationship management synergies. Overall, a defined CREM strategy helps organizations increase customer satisfaction, retention, and profitability by effectively managing customer relationships.

In their study, Auwal *et al.* (2022), highlight the critical importance of the quality and adequacy of facilities in buildings. They emphasize that well-managed and wellmaintained structures significantly enhance the overall functionality and usability of the buildings. The study suggests that investing in high-quality facilities and ensuring their proper upkeep can lead to improved satisfaction and better performance of the buildings over time. The study underscores the need for ongoing management and maintenance to preserve the value and utility of building structures.

Corporate real estate management (CREM) has a significant impact on organizational performance, but it also faces challenges. The study by Opoku *et al.* (2022) found that organizational culture, specifically entrepreneurial culture, contributes to a substantial rise in employee performance, leading to increased profitability.

Additionally, Rahman *et al.* (2022) discovered that sustainable corporate real estate elements such as energy management, workspace management, and innovation management significantly affect business performance. Ntene *et al.* (2020) emphasized the importance of a proactive approach to corporate real estate management to create value through real estate portfolios, which can improve overall organizational performance. Another study by Abolo (2023), showed that increasing investment in corporate real estate can actually decrease firm performance.

Additionally, Seger and Pfnür (2020) found that ownership of corporate real estate can have an impact on firm performance, with additional business activities influencing the relevance of ownership. Furthermore, Feng and Goli (2023) demonstrated that corporate financial performance can be influenced by corporate real estate management, specifically through the mediation of earnings management. Nanda *et al.*, (2021) highlighted the significance of proper management of corporate real estate, as it is a key cost factor in the corporate budget. Amos and Boakye-Agyeman (2023) tested the content validity of value-adding indicators in the context of corporate real estate management practices in Ghana.

Additionally, Nuryana and Surjandari (2019), showed that corporate governance mechanisms positively influence a company's financial performance and have a negative effect on earnings management. According to Al Aina and Atan (2020), factors such as work environment, training and development, and leadership play a crucial role in determining organizational performance. Additionally, the implementation of an efficient organizational culture has been found to result in high productivity and satisfaction, leading to increased profitability (Alrazehi *et al.*, 2021).

Furthermore, Tamunomiebi and Worgu (2020), assert that talent management, including talent attraction, retention, and development, has also been found to significantly impact employee performance, which in turn affects organizational performance. These findings suggest that the relationship between corporate real estate management and financial performance is complex and can be influenced by factors such as corporate governance and social responsibility. Overall, these studies highlight the crucial role of corporate real estate management in enhancing organizational performance in the banking sector.

One of the challenges according to Urbonavičius *et al.* (2023) is the need for strategic corporate real estate risk management to enhance performance. Another challenge is the lack of complete adoption of strategic CREM practices in some organizations, indicating that CRE is not strategically managed like other corporate resources (Donkor-Hyiaman *et al.*, 2021 & Boakye-Agyeman *et al.*, 2022).

Additionally, the real estate industry faces capital restraints, which can hinder the survival and competitiveness of enterprises (Adiyanto, 2021). Despite these challenges, CREM leaders are continuously seeking new avenues

for expense control and topline revenue growth. Overall, while CREM has the potential to improve organizational performance, it is important to address these challenges to fully realize its benefits.

The existing literature on CREM has notable shortcomings. Previous studies often focus on single aspects of CREM, such as space and workplace management, rather than taking a holistic view of the interrelatedness of different CREM variables. Moreover, these studies commonly rely on subjective measures, such as self-reported satisfaction scores, rather than objective metrics like output or revenue data.

Furthermore, research predominantly originates from developed regions neglecting the distinctive context and challenges faced in developing nations like Nigeria. Additionally, the reliance on cross-sectional data in these studies hampers the establishment of causal relationships and the analysis of dynamic changes over time. To bridge these gaps, this study conducts a thorough analysis of CREM's influence on organizational productivity and performance within the banking sector in Bauchi metropolis, Nigeria, an essential sector accounting for a significant portion of the country's GDP and employment.

Methodology

A quantitative research design was adopted for this study, using a survey method to collect data from a sample of banks in Bauchi metropolis, Nigeria. The survey consisted of a structured questionnaire that measured the variables of interest. The target population for this study are banks operating in Bauchi metropolis, Nigeria. The sample size of 86 was determined using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970), table of sample size determination. Out of a total of 86 questionnaires that were distributed to the respondents, only 78 were retrieved.

A stratified random sampling technique was utilized to select a representative sample of banks from Bauchi Metropolis. The stratified random sampling technique is justified for this study due to the heterogeneous nature of the banking sector. The technique ensures a comprehensive representation of different stakeholders, allowing for meaningful comparisons between strata and enhancing the statistical precision of the study. By addressing the study's objectives to assess CREM impact, identify key variables, and understand stakeholder perceptions, the stratified

Data Analysis And Discussion sampling method mitigates biases and provides a robust foundation for in-depth analysis and reliable conclusions. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire, the questionnaire utilized closed-ended questions which employed 5-point Likert scales or multiple-choice options to gather quantitative data, allowing for the measurement of respondents' opinions and perceptions the 5-point Likert scale used SD = Strongly Disagree (1), D = Disagree (2), N = Neutral (3), A = Agree (4), SA = Strongly Agree (5).

The data analysis involved the use of descriptive statistics (weighted mean) or analyzing closed-ended questions. The Likert scale responses were examined to identify trends and patterns in participants' views. To ensure ethical considerations, participants' confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the study.

The data analysis in Table 1 reveals the extent to which CREM influences organizational productivity and performance in the banking sector of Bauchi metropolis, it becomes evident that the majority of respondents hold a positive view (agree/strongly agree) regarding the impact of CREM practices.

According to Pfnuer *et al.* (2021), aligning real estate strategies with organizational objectives is crucial for enhancing financial efficiency and overall performance. The positive responses from the participants align with this perspective, indicating that CREM practices significantly enhance overall organizational productivity within the banking sector of Bauchi metropolis.

Table 1: Influence of CREM in Organizational Productivity and Performance in Banking Sector of Bauchi Metropolis.

Statement	SD(1)	D(2)	N(3)	A(4)	SA(5)	MEAN
CREM practices enhance overall organizational productivity.	2 (2.6%)	4 (5.1%)	10 (12.8%)	38 (48.7%)	24 (30.8%)	4.00
Effective CREM positively impacts the financial performance (profitability, cost reduction) of banks.	1 (1.3%)	6 (7.7%)	12 (15.4%)	37 (47.4%)	22 (28.2%)	3.94
CREM strategies contribute to improved customer satisfaction and service quality.	3 (3.8%)	8 (10.3%)	14 (17.9%)	35 (44.9%)	18 (23.1%)	3.73
Efficient space utilization through CREM leads to enhanced employee productivity.	1 (1.3%)	5 (6.4%)	11 (14.1%)	36 (46.2%)	25 (32.1%)	4.02

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Moreover, this finding correlates with the research conducted by Ali and Anwar (2021) and Boakye-Agyeman *et al.* (2021), emphasizing the positive influence of effective CREM on financial performance, including profitability and cost reduction.

The acknowledgement by 75.6% of participants regarding this positive impact reflects the importance of strategic corporate real estate management in contributing to a bank's financial stability. This aligns with prior studies that have emphasized the strategic aspects of corporate real estate management, highlighting its significance in improving overall performance and competitiveness.

Additionally, the responses indicating that 68% of participants agree that CREM strategies contribute to improved customer satisfaction and service quality align with the findings of Opoku *et al.* (2022). Effective CREM strategies can enhance customer satisfaction by providing conducive and innovative environments, thereby positively influencing customer experiences. The alignment between the respondents' views and prior research emphasizes the role of CREM in not only internal organizational aspects but also in shaping customer interactions and relationships.

Furthermore, a substantial percentage of participants (78.3%) affirm that efficient space utilization through CREM leads to enhanced employee productivity. This finding resonates with the study conducted by Haynes *et*

al. (2017), highlighting the importance of efficient space utilization strategies. Properly designed and utilized spaces contribute to healthier and more comfortable work environments, leading to higher job satisfaction and increased employee engagement. The positive responses underscore the significance of CREM in creating workspaces that foster productivity and employee well-being.

However, the data also reveals areas for improvement. The responses in the "Neutral" and "Disagree" categories concerning CREM strategies related to customer satisfaction indicate a potential gap in aligning real estate practices with customer needs. Addressing these concerns is essential for organizations to ensure that CREM strategies are not only internally focused but also customer-oriented. A more customer-centric approach can further enhance the overall customer experience, positively impacting the bank's reputation and competitiveness. The overall insights reveal a strong positive perception of CREM practices, with means close to or above 4 for all statements, indicating general consensus on their benefits. The highest agreement is on the impact of space utilization on employee productivity, highlighting the importance of efficient space management. Financial performance and productivity are also highly valued outcomes. While the impact on customer satisfaction is positive, there is more neutrality and disagreement, suggesting a need for further exploration or better communication. These insights can help organizations prioritize CREM initiatives, focusing on space utilization and productivity while addressing scepticism about customer satisfaction impacts.

Table 2: Key CREM variables affecting productivity and performance in the Banking Sector of Bauchi Metropolis.

Statement	SD(1)	D(2)	N(3)	A(4)	SA(5)	MEAN
Cost optimization strategies in CREM positively impact the organization's financial outcomes.	2 (2.6%)	7 (9.0%)	13 (16.7%)	32 (41.0%)	24 (30.8%)	3.89
Effective CREM positively impacts financial performance (profitability, cost reduction) of banks.	2 (2.6%)	6 (7.7%)	12 (15.4%)	33 (42.3%)	25 (32.1%)	3.94
Technological integration in CREM practices improves operational efficiency.	3 (3.8%)	5 (6.4%)	14 (17.9%)	32 (41.0%)	24 (30.8%)	3.88
Employee satisfaction initiatives in CREM positively influence overall organizational performance	2 (2.6%)	8 (10.3%)	15 (19.2%)	30 (38.5%)	23 (29.5%)	3.82

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

In general, the findings align with the existing literature on CREM's positive influence on organizational productivity and performance. While there is a strong foundation in CREM practices enhancing productivity and financial performance, addressing specific concerns related to customer satisfaction can lead to a more comprehensive and impactful implementation of CREM strategies within the banking sector of Bauchi metropolis.

Table 2 clearly identified the key CREM variables that significantly affect organizational productivity and performance in the banking sector of Bauchi metropolis. The data reflects the participants' collective recognition of the pivotal role of specific CREM variables in driving productivity and performance within the banking sector. A significant proportion of respondents (71.8%) concur that cost optimization strategies in CREM have a positive impact on the organization's financial outcomes. This aligns with the findings of Pfnuer *et al.* (2021), which emphasized the importance of strategic cost management. The positive consensus indicates that effectively

managing costs through CREM initiatives is not only acknowledged but also valued as a means to enhance the financial health of banking institutions in Bauchi metropolis. This insight resonates with the emphasis on strategic corporate real estate management to establish financial efficiency and competitiveness, as highlighted by BoakyeAgyeman *et al.* (2022).

Similarly, the data reveals that 71.8% of respondents concur that technological integration in CREM practices improves operational efficiency. This reflects the acknowledgement of technology's role in streamlining operations within the banking sector, which, in turn, contributes to improved productivity and performance. This finding resonates with the views of Fauzi *et al.* (2017), who emphasized the significance of technology in corporate real estate management.

Technological integration is instrumental in optimizing business processes, ensuring efficient operations, and enhancing productivity. This alignment highlights the consensus among the participants regarding the importance of technological advancements in CREM practices to drive operational efficiency and overall performance.

Furthermore, 68% of participants agreed that employee satisfaction initiatives in CREM positively influence overall organizational performance. This finding underscores the recognition of the intrinsic link between employee contentment, organizational culture, and overall productivity within banking institutions. The alignment with the studies of Nanda (2021) and Boakye-

Agyeman *et al.* (2022), emphasizes the understanding that fostering employee satisfaction leads to increased productivity and, consequently, improved organizational performance. This reflects the consensus that initiatives focused on employee wellbeing, satisfaction, and development contribute significantly to the banking sector's overall success.

The general insights reveal a strong positive perception of CREM practices, with mean scores close to or above 3.8 for all statements, highlighting their broad benefits. Cost optimization and financial performance received particularly high means of 3.89 and 3.94, respectively. Technological integration scored 3.88, indicating strong support for its role in operational efficiency. Employee satisfaction initiatives scored 3.82, showing positive views but with more neutrality and disagreement, suggesting a need for better communication. These insights can help organizations prioritize CREM initiatives, focusing on cost optimization, financial performance, and technological integration, while addressing scepticism about employee satisfaction.

Table 3: Understanding stakeholders' perception on the added value of CREM in the banking sector in Bauchi metropolis

Statement	SD(1)	D(2)	N(3)	A(4)	SA(5)	MEAN
Stakeholders recognize CREM as a crucial factor for the bank's competitiveness.	1 (1.3%)	3 (3.8%)	9 (11.5%)	36 (46.2%)	29 (37.2%)	4.14
CREM initiatives are perceived as contributing significantly to the bank's brand image.	2 (2.6%)	7 (9.0%)	14 (17.9%)	31 (39.7%)	24 (30.8%)	3.86
Stakeholders believe that CREM positively impacts customer experiences and relationships.	3 (3.8%)	6 (7.7%)	11 (14.1%)	34 (43.6%)	24 (30.8%)	4.05
CREM practices are seen as essential for long-term sustainability and growth of the bank.	2 (2.6%)	4 (5.1%)	10 (12.8%)	35 (44.9%)	27 (34.6%)	4.31

Source: Field Survey, 2023

In summary, this study's findings provide valuable insights into the key CREM variables that significantly impact organizational productivity and performance within the banking sector of Bauchi metropolis. Cost optimization, effective CREM, technological integration, and employee satisfaction emerge as central elements contributing to

the sector's efficiency and success. Addressing these variables effectively can lead to improved financial outcomes, employee productivity, and overall organizational performance, aligning with the principles of CREM emphasized in the existing literature.

Analyzing the responses in Table 3, which delves into how stakeholders in the banking sector of Bauchi metropolis perceive and evaluate the added value of CREM, provides valuable insights into the stakeholders' perspectives, aligning with the existing literature on CREM's multifaceted impact.

The data reveals that a significant majority of respondents (83.4%) agree that stakeholders recognize CREM as a crucial factor for the bank's competitiveness. This finding resonates with the insights of Ali and Anwar (2021) and Boakye-Agyeman *et al.* (2022), who emphasize the strategic significance of CREM in enhancing competitiveness. The strong consensus among stakeholders underscores the recognition of CREM's pivotal role in enhancing the competitive edge of banks in Bauchi metropolis. This aligns with the notion that CREM is not only an operational strategy but also a strategic asset that directly influences a bank's market position and competitiveness.

Furthermore, 70.5% of the participants believe that CREM initiatives significantly contribute to the bank's brand image. This result emphasizes CREM's role in shaping the public perception of banks, aligning with the findings of Haynes *et al.* (2017). The acknowledgement of CREM's impact on external reputation highlights its role not only in internal operations but also in crafting a positive public image. Stakeholders' perceptions in this regard indicate an understanding of the interconnectedness between physical workspace management and brand perception, essential elements for building trust and credibility in the banking sector.

Moreover, 74.4% of stakeholders agree that CREM positively impacts customer experiences and relationships. This insight aligns with the studies of Osmadi and Kaluthanthri (2019), emphasizing that a well-implemented CRM strategy enhances customer interactions and satisfaction. The stakeholders' acknowledgement of CREM's influence on customer experiences underscores the strategy's role in fostering positive interactions, improving satisfaction levels, and nurturing long-term relationships. These aspects are fundamental in the banking sector, where customer trust and loyalty are paramount for sustained success.

Additionally, 79.5% of participants believe that CREM practices are essential for the long-term sustainability and growth of the bank. This high level of agreement underscores stakeholders' understanding of CREM as a fundamental strategy for ensuring the future viability and expansion of banking institutions. This aligns with the emphasis on strategic corporate real estate management for financial stability, as highlighted by Opoku *et al.* (2022).

The stakeholders' recognition of CREM's role in long-term sustainability emphasizes its strategic importance in guiding the future trajectory of banking institutions, aligning with the principles of Corporate Real Estate Sustainable Management (CRESM) outlined by Osmadi and Kaluthanthri (2019) and Fauzi *et al.* (2017).

In general, the responses reflect a widespread recognition among stakeholders of the vital role played by CREM in enhancing competitiveness, shaping brand image, improving customer experiences, and ensuring the long-term sustainability and growth of banks in the Bauchi metropolis banking sector. These perceptions highlight the strategic significance of CREM practices in the eyes of stakeholders, emphasizing the need for continued emphasis on effective CREM strategies within the banking industry. The alignment between stakeholders' perceptions and the existing literature underlines the critical importance of CREM in shaping the multifaceted aspects of banking operations and reputation management.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The analysis of responses to the research questions reveals positive perceptions regarding the impact of CREM practices in the banking sector of Bauchi metropolis. Aligning with prior studies, participants acknowledged CREM's significant role in enhancing financial efficiency, profitability, and cost reduction, contributing to the financial health of banking institutions. The study reaffirmed CREM's importance in customer satisfaction, emphasizing the need for customer-oriented real estate practices. Efficient space utilization's positive influence on employee productivity was recognized, highlighting the importance of well-designed workspaces in fostering employee satisfaction and engagement.

The findings emphasized key CREM variables, including cost optimization, effective CREM, technological integration, and employee satisfaction, as central elements influencing organizational productivity and performance. Banking institutions are recommended to refine CREM strategies related to customer satisfaction, implementing a more customer-centric approach for enhanced reputation and competitiveness. Strategic cost management should be prioritized to enhance financial efficiency, aligning with the principles of CREM highlighted in the existing literature.

Investment in innovative workspace design is crucial, given the consensus on the role of flexible and adaptable office spaces in employee productivity. Moreover, continuous investments in technology are essential to streamline operations and boost overall productivity, aligning with the views of prior research. Employee satisfaction initiatives should be emphasized, focusing on well-being, satisfaction, and development, acknowledging the link between employee contentment and organizational performance.

Additionally, banking institutions should integrate sustainability practices into their CREM strategies, ensuring long-term sustainability and growth, in line with principles outlined by existing literature. The alignment between stakeholders' perceptions and the existing literature underscores the strategic significance of CREM. Therefore, a continuous emphasis on the effective implementation of CREM strategies within the industry is crucial. These recommendations collectively provide a roadmap for banking institutions to optimize CREM benefits, enhance organizational productivity and performance, and remain competitive in Bauchi metropolis' financial landscape.

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